

Terranes Involved in the Variscan Suture from NW Iberia: A Review of Their Origin and Tectonothermal Evolution

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NW Iberia includes an excellent section of the Variscan suture, where different terranes with continental or oceanic affinities appear with clear structural relationships. The great exposures in the Cantabrian coastal section (Cabo Ortegal and Órdenes complexes, and the Malpica-Tui Unit) are a unique natural laboratory to approach the origin of the terranes involved in the suture zone and their internal structure and tectonothermal evolution. Three groups of terranes and a lower tectonic mélangé constitute the huge allochthonous pile thrust over the Iberian autochthonous and parautochthonous domains, the section of the Gondwanan margin not involved in continental subduction during the Variscan deformation (Schistose Domain of Galicia-Trás-os-Montes and Central Iberian Zone). The allochthonous terranes are formed, from top to bottom, by upper units, ophiolitic units, basal units and lower mélangé.

In the upper units, c. 12.000 m of terrigenous sediments intruded by large massifs of cambrian calc-alkaline granitoids (I-type) and tholeiitic gabbros with some bodies of ultramafic rocks, are considered to represent a section of a magmatic arc, built up in the periphery of Gondwana during Neoproterozoic-Cambrian times. The Nd model ages from a topmost turbiditic series (Ares-Sada greywackes) show close relationships with some Avalonian terranes, suggesting proximity in the paleomargin of Gondwana. A section of this arc rifted from the continent in Early Ordovician time, drifted towards the North and opened a wide Paleozoic oceanic domain, the Rheic Ocean. An uppermost part of this terrane affected by metamorphism ranging between the greenschist facies and the low pressure granulite facies, dated at 496-484 Ma, is a relic preserving almost intact the tectonothermal activity occurred in the peri-Gondwanan arc. Otherwise, the lower part shows a generalized high P-T event dated at c. 400 Ma developing extensive recrystallization in the eclogite and granulite facies. This subduction related event marks the accretion of this arc-derived terrane to the southern margin of Laurussia during Early Devonian times, coinciding with the widest spreading of the Rheic Ocean right before starting to contract.

True MORB ophiolites derived from the Rheic Ocean lithosphere are unknown in the suture zone of NW Iberia. On the contrary, this ocean is represented by a group of island-arc tholeiitic mafic units (supra-subduction zone type) suggesting two critical moments in its evolution: a first Late Cambrian stage (c. 500 Ma, Vila de Cruces Unit) representing the opening of peri-Gondwanan back-arc basins which are the origin of this ocean; a second stage dated at c. 395 Ma (Careón Unit) marking the activity of intra-Rheic subduction zones that removed completely the older and cold lithosphere developed in the mid-Rheic Ocean ridge, which also disappeared during the closure of this ocean. Due to their buoyant nature, the ophiolites generated during this stage scaped from early-Variscan subduction and they are the most common ophiolites preserved in the Variscan suture across Europe. Apart from the Rheic Ocean ophiolites, other mafic and ultramafic sections in NW Iberia have been related to Cambrian-Ordovician accretionary stages affecting sections of the peri-Gondwanan ocean, i.e. in previous moments to the opening of the Rheic Ocean. This is the case of the Bazar Unit, which appears accreted below the arc-derived terrane in the western part of the Órdenes Complex and it is considered to preserve a section of the Iapetus-Tornquist Ocean.

The basal units are formed by a thick sequence of Ediacaran-Early Ordovician terrigenous metasediments intruded by granitoids (calc-alkaline to peralkaline) and other mafic igneous rocks.

These units are considered to represent the most external part of the Gondwanan paleomargin, with an original position located further to the East than the arc-related section preserved in the upper units. The basal units are a continental subduction complex, where continental layers were subducted towards the W-SW (present coordinates) and imbricated below previously accreted ophiolites at c. 370 Ma, at the onset of the Variscan deformation. This subduction finished the closure of the Rheic Ocean and is the first true Variscan deformation affecting the margin of Gondwana. A variety of C-type eclogites, blueschists and lawsonite bearing metabasites developed during this second high-P event affecting the materials assembled in the allochthonous pile. In detail, the basal units can be subdivided in two main groups according to their tectonothermal evolution: an upper group with high-P and medium-high-T metamorphism (Aigualada and Espasante units); and a lower group with high-P and low-medium-T metamorphism (Cean, Malpica-Tui, Santiago, Lalín and Forcarei units). The whole ensemble represents a well preserved paleosubduction zone, the Variscan subduction zone, with the upper group representing the sector in contact with the mantle wedge, and the lower part preserving a section of the cooler slices that were underthrust later. The accretion of new continental slices finally blocked the subduction. However, continental convergence did not declined during the Mississippian, thus triggering the transference of the allochthonous pile and the Rheic suture onto the Gondwana mainland followed by the extensional collapse of the collisional wedge. The convergence remained during the Pennsylvanian and produced further reworking of the allochthonous nappe pile in strike-slip systems.

Finally, the Somozas *mélange* is the frontal *mélange* zone developed between the mantle wedge and the section of the Gondwanan margin under subduction. It is a piece of the subduction channel with c. 500 m of serpentinite *mélange* containing variably sized blocks of metasediments, volcanics, gabbros, granitoids and several high-P rocks. The subducted continental margin was exhumed later on and emplaced over the *mélange* zone, that appears now as a unique element located at the contact between the allochthonous terranes and the parautochthonous Schistose Domain.